

PROBLEMS OF EMPLOYEES IN SOFTWARE INDUSTRIES IN CHENNAI CITY

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Abstract

For academic staff especially in software industries, it needs to be productive; they need to have stressful works and attached task. Employee perception of problems, such as health and work related issues, may impact performance at work, which could lead to a decrease in publications, a drop in quality, and a reduction in research funding. To learn how, or whether, the perceived decline is impacted by the stated issues, whether alone or in conjunction with motivation for work and job attitudes, few research have focused on productivity loss within academic personnel. Performance in software industries is very variable and is impacted by alterations to health and employment position, necessitating this type of design. Employees who encountered related to health or work environment issues also had greater degrees of motivation, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment, which were linked to lower levels of output loss. Employees in software industries with a combination of issues showed much fewer instances of productivity loss when they had strong levels of dedication and drive at work. In conclusion, work motivation, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment all have an impact on decreased productivity among academic employees. These factors appear to buffer, or moderate, the decline in productivity for this group of employees, in addition to health-related issues or issues with the workplace.

Keywords: Employees, Performance, Software Industries, Productivity, Issues, Health.

INTRODUCTION

Many of India's cities, including Mumbai, Kolkata, Delhi, Bangalore, Hyderabad, and Chennai, are home to some of the most significant software and computer technology companies in the nation. India is quickly becoming a global leader in information and technology. The software sector is growing quickly in this area of Chennai. This is because the area serves as a focal point for numerous multinational and Indian software industrial bases, who are setting up shop there. The creation of numerous cutting-edge technologies has been made possible by the explosive growth of the software industry. The growth of many cities' urban infrastructures is also aided by the software sector. As software solutions become a common new feature in several places.

The information technology industry has grown tremendously as a result of new technologies and innovations, yet there is now a severe lack of qualified people. Elite employee recruitment, retention, and motivation are ongoing challenges in this industry. Human resources have to be proactive in enticing top personnel with attractive benefits and incentives in a sector where competent individuals are hard to come by. The IT industry faces difficulties in recruiting and educating new technical talent. The software industry is a rigorous and difficult career.

Developers frequently become frustrated at work due to the growing complexity of their software projects, time restraints, and a lack of resources. The difficulties maintaining personal hygiene, nighttime work issues, cervical issues, early aging, disputes in software evaluation businesses, cyber security, the use of AI and automated processes, a lack of alignment between consumers and provide needs, mismanaged timelines, and the significance of quality assurance are among the issues that employees face.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Souza (2022), Work from home, remote-first teams, dispersed teams, and hybrids (part-remote/part-office) teams will undoubtedly become more prevalent, while the long-term ramifications of the COVID-19 pandemic on software professionals and companies are difficult to estimate. Investigating the difficulties that software teams and organizations encounter with new remote and hybrid work is crucial. As a result, this paper presents the results of a participant observation, grounded constructivist theory study that looked at the effects of working from home on developing software over the course of a year. A software team coordination theory was developed as a result of this investigation.

In a nutshell, moving from office to homework significantly changed how software teams coordinated. While group cohesion and improved communication seem protective, mistrust, poor parenting, and communication bricolage undermine coordination. Misunderstandings, requests for assistance, lower levels of satisfaction with work among team members, and more vaguely defined assignments are just a few of the issues caused by poor coordination.

These issues consequently lower overall project success and force experts to switch from Scrum to Kanab as their preferred method of software development. Our research suggests that software companies with a large number of remote workers can increase performance by fostering stronger teamwork and providing assistance to workers who have childcare and family commitments.

Yazdonov (2022), one of the key elements affecting the social and financial effectiveness of the company is how the workplace is set up. The management of the workplace entails a variety of tasks that enable you to give employees the conditions they need for extremely productive and safe work, boost the content and allure of the workforce, and protect their health. The office's full and comprehensive equipment helps to improve the effectiveness and standard of how the job is organized.

Cetindamar (2022), seeks to comprehend the meaning and components of literacy in artificial intelligence (AI). Few researches have looked into how employees' AI literacy relates to organizational affordances that digital technologies, particularly AI, cause in the workplace. To profile the academic landscape and identify the important research themes and pertinent articles connected to AI literacy's the definition, dimensions, problems, and future directions, descriptive statistics, keyword overlap analysis, and an organizational topic tree are used.

The results emphasize four categories of skills linked to AI literacy: technological, professional, work-related, human-machine related, and learning-related skills. This underlines the significance of implementing AI literacy for non-AI professionals. By providing a fresh conceptualization of AI literate and connecting it to the employee's function in digital workplaces, this study adds to the literature related to technology management studies. In order to improve the design and application of AI, we invite academics to investigate the impact of employee-technology engagements on employees' AI literacy.

Catherine (2022), Stress is a typical aspect of contemporary living. Although worry doesn't constitute a mental disorder, it is very closely linked to it. Because of workplace pressures or environmental concerns, oppression is frequently present in organizations or in any profession. Emotional, bodily, and moral issues will result from this. It is a difficult condition when there is a lot of job-related congestion that interferes with employees' ability to focus and their regular working environment. This investigation was carried out in Hosur, Tamil Nadu, India, at a prestigious manufacturing facility. Studying employee stress reduction as a means of performance management tool was the primary goal. Through the use of straightforward random sample procedures and the lottery method, the researcher chose 100 employees. 57% of the respondents indicated moderate levels of stress, according to the study's findings. 67% of respondents indicated having minimal job stress, compared to 84% who indicated intermediate level stress connected to their workplace. The study also revealed that 69% of respondents had poor quality of life, which negatively impacted their ability to execute their jobs.

Importance

Software Industries in India is turning into a stress hub, by which lot of new problems are occurring in a daily basis, by which the productivity affects by which work lot and pressure can't be handled by the employees.

Objective of the study

1. To study the problems faced by the employees working in Software Industries.
2. To give best solution for the problems faced by employees working in software industries.

Hypotheses

The study is based on objectives the following null hypothesis was formulated and tested for the study.

H₀: There is no significant difference between employee demographic variable and problems.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Both primary and secondary data are used to support the current investigation. Primary data are gathered from a variety personnel working in software companies. Additional information should be gathered from a variety of books, publications, journals, articles, theses, websites,

and other sources. The gathering, processing, and interpretation of primary data satisfy all the study's goals. The well-designed interview schedule with a 5-point Likert scale will be used to gather data on work-life balance.

Sample Design

The approach of random samples was used to get the main data. Questionnaire was used to perform a field survey. The customers participating in the trial is using a straight forward random sampling technique, with 600 as sample size consisting 200 each from Software Companies in Chennai.

S.No	Name of the Software Industries	No. of Respondents
1	Accenture	200
2	Brilasoftware	200
3	HCL Technologies	200
TOTAL		600

Statistical Tools

The Mean and simple percentage analysis has been used to analyze the connection toward satisfaction of customers in banking sectors.

Table 1: List of Problems Faced by Employees in Software Companies

S. No	Particulars	SA	A	N	D	SD	Total	Mean
1.	Feeling of safe at work environment	299	194	55	29	23	600	2.47
		49.83	32.33	9.17	4.83	3.83	100.00	
2.	Works during night time is safe	195	130	33	57	185	600	3.09
		32.50	21.67	5.50	9.50	30.83	100.00	
3.	Very difficult in maintaining health and hygiene	113	157	24	46	260	600	2.70
		18.83	26.17	4.00	7.67	43.33	100.00	
4.	Early aging due to heavy work load and change of timings	213	110	23	47	207	600	3.13
		35.50	18.33	3.83	7.83	34.50	100.00	
5.	Issues related to eyesight	134	161	27	42	236	600	2.86
		22.33	26.83	4.50	7.00	39.33	100.00	
6.	Availability of transportation facilities especially during night shift works	201	99	51	55	194	600	3.10
		33.50	16.50	8.50	9.17	32.33	100.00	
7.	Workloads and work pressure	94	196	30	38	242	600	2.77
		15.67	32.67	5.00	6.33	40.33	100.00	
8.	Issues related to Cervical and spine	113	174	24	48	241	600	2.78
		18.83	29.00	4.00	8.00	40.17	100.00	
9.	Work interest starts reducing due to stress and pressure	90	204	34	30	242	600	2.78
		15.00	34.00	5.67	5.00	40.33	100.00	
10.	Issues related to health and its frequencies are increasing	259	164	23	54	100	600	2.65
		43.17	27.33	3.83	9.00	16.67	100.00	

Source: Primary Data

The table 1 shows that the feeling of safe at work environment is strongly agreed by 299 respondents out of 600 i.e., 49.83, and 23 respondents strongly disagree the statement, works during night time is safe as the statement is strongly agreed by 32.50 of the respondents 195, the respondents 46 have disagree that it's very difficult in maintaining health and hygiene especially during working hours, 35.50 percent of the respondents strongly agreed that the software industries work causes early aging, 161 respondents agree (26.83 percent) that eye sight related issues occur due to working hours and constant looking at screen light, availability of transportation facilities especially during night shift works the statement has been strongly disagreed by 194 respondents (32.33 percent), 196 respondents agree that the workloads and work pressure is there at 32.67 percent, the respondents strongly agree that issues related to Cervical and spine is high that is 113 respondents (18.83 percent). Working interest keeps on decreasing as 204 respondents agree the statement with 34 percent, the health issue and its frequency also high as 164 respondents out of 600 agree the statement with 27.33 percent.

Table 2: Age and Employee Problems

Factors	Group Mean					F Statistic	Sig.
	Employee Age						
	21-30 years	31-40 years	41-50 years	Above 50 years	Total		
Feeling of safe at work environment	1.93	2.58	2.48	2.75	2.47	4.916	0.002*
Works during night time is safe	2.69	3.26	3.41	3.77	3.28	6.956	0.001*
Very difficult in maintaining health and hygiene	2.55	3.12	2.93	3.46	3.03	4.747	0.003*
Early aging due to heavy work load and change of timings	2.59	3.28	3.19	3.56	3.19	5.680	0.001*
Issues related to eyesight	2.88	2.90	3.37	3.51	3.10	4.882	0.002*
Availability of transportation facilities especially during night shift works	2.59	3.14	3.48	3.54	3.20	7.189	0.001*
Workloads and work pressure	2.48	3.01	3.10	3.39	3.00	4.961	0.002*
Issues related to Cervical and spine	2.70	2.93	3.17	3.33	3.01	2.856	0.036*
Work interest starts reducing due to stress and pressure	2.42	2.86	3.14	3.14	2.90	4.893	0.002*
Issues related to health and its frequencies are increasing	2.59	2.71	2.88	3.32	2.82	3.386	0.018*

Source: Computations based on Primary Data * Sig.@5%

Table 2 shows that the employee problems on the basis of age, the age category above fifty years are having higher acceptance than the other age category of employee with mean score of 2.75, 3.77, 3.46, 3.56, 3.51, 3.54, 3.39, 3.33, 3.14 and 3.32 respectively. This analysis shows the problems of aged category of employees is higher when compared with young age category of employees in IT companies. This is proved that the F value of the above respective grievances variables of 4.916, 6.956, 4.747, 5.680, 4.882, 7.189, 4.961, 2.856, 4.893 and 3.386 are significant at five percent. Hence, the stated hypothesis is rejected. Hence, this analysis proved that aged category of employees is higher problems than the young age category of employees in the IT companies.

Findings

1. 161 respondents agree (26.83%) that eye sight related issues occur due to heavy working hours and constant looking at screen and screen time.
2. Issues related to health and its frequencies are increasing as 259 respondents out of 600 strongly agree the statement i.e., 43.17%.
3. Early aging due to heavy work load and change of timings as the statement is agreed by 110 respondents i.e., 18.33%.

Suggestions

1. This study found that the employees feeling insecure especially working during night shift and availability of transportation facility during mid-night is very difficult so, for this situation exclusive bus can be provided from the management side for the welfare of employees. And mostly companies can try their to maximum not to include women during night working hours.
2. It is also observed that frequent health issues faced by employees for this the companies can conduct frequent health checkups also its essential to maintain a separate record for each and every persons health status need to be observed.
3. Frequent breaks and some sort of essential distractions like recreation clubs, need to be provided for the employees to improve the productivity and work enhancement.

CONCLUSION

We stated at the outset that computer software and globalization presented opportunities as well as difficulties for emerging nations. We discover, however, that the availability of infrastructure and educational credentials are the two key factors in successfully addressing the challenge and utilizing the opportunities. This brings us full round to the main finding of many development discussions over the previous few decades: underdeveloped economies have subpar infrastructure and weak educational foundations.

We now understand that while the sector gives underdeveloped nations a chance to get around capital restrictions, it nevertheless benefits those with excellent infrastructure and educational levels. Despite, generally infrastructure and educational levels, this business has succeeded in some nations, such as India, due to a combination of factors. While things are getting better, the government needs to step up its game to guarantee that the rewards from these software industries are distributed more fairly.

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